

JUVENILE RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS AFTER COVID 19: A CASE HISTORY

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Annotation. Juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (JRA) is a chronic systemic inflammatory disease of connective tissue, characterized by progressive erosive-destructive polyarthritis and rapid development of functional disorders in the affected joints. One of the reasons for the appearance of JRA symptoms is previous infectious diseases. Now the number of patients after infection with Covid 19 is growing significantly, especially among young children. Outbreaks of rheumatic diseases in children have been described following SARS-CoV-2 infection in several cohorts. The impact of SARS-CoV-2 infection on the course of JRA is not yet known. However, more research is needed to establish the true risk of exacerbation of JRA with COVID-19 [1]. The COVID-19 infection occurs much less commonly in children than in adults, presumably due to the predominance of asymptomatic variants. Nevertheless, single deaths by the COVID-19 were reported in children worldwide. Some of these deaths result from multisystem inflammatory syndrome (MIS) that develops at late stages or after the COVID-19 [2].

Introduction. In modern conditions, post-Covid syndrome (PCS) is characterized by clinical heterogeneity and multiorgan involvement, often representing a differential diagnostic and therapeutic problem [3].

Today, there are about 20 million people suffering from rheumatoid arthritis (RA) in the world who have been infected with SARS-CoV-2 at least once since the beginning of the pandemic in 2020. In a comparative cohort study of the clinical course and outcomes of COVID-19, performed by K.M. D'Silva et al. in a number of regions of the United States with the highest epidemiological indicators of this infection in patients with immunoinflammatory rheumatic diseases (IIRD), among which RA predominated, such patients more often required treatment in an intensive care unit and additional oxygenation (relative risk (RR) 3.11 at 95% -nom confidence interval (CI) 1.07–9.05) [4]. In a study conducted by T.Y. Hsu et al., an analysis of medical records of hospitalized patients showed that severe complications more often occurred with IIRD, including hyperinflammatory syndrome (macrophage activation syndrome) [5,6].

It is known that viral infections, including those caused by coronaviruses, are a trigger for the development and exacerbation of IIRD. It is believed that PCS may modify the course of RA by exacerbating systemic inflammation [7,8].

However, despite the accumulated clinical experience and large-scale vaccination, a number of questions remain unresolved regarding the influence of SARS-CoV-2 on the course and prognosis of RA, as well as other IIRD [9].

Case presentation. A 5-year-old male patient was hospitalized in the cardiorheumatology department of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Pediatrics (RSSPMCP) for inpatient treatment with complaints of pain and swelling in the knees, restricted movement, inability to walk, morning stiffness and fever. From the patient's medical history the mother became infected with COVID-19 in September 2023 but, the child did not have any symptoms, it can be seen that the patient had Covid 19 without symptoms and in a mild form. In January 2024, 5 months after contacting Covid 19, the patient was unable to walk after waking up

in the kindergarten. Then, his mother gave him one tablet ibuprofen at home. But the condition has not any positive changes. Unfortunately, other signs will appear such as swelling both of the knee joints and prolonged fever. After that, they went to the RSSPMCP. During the examination, it was revealed that the child had limited movement in the knee joints and swelling. Full flexion and extension of the knee joint is limited. Cry when moving, especially when walking, due to severe pain. The temperature remained at the level of febrile figures.

Laboratory findings. Physical examination showed signs of inflammation supported by laboratory findings, i.e., elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and leukocytes. Hematological parameters are presented in **Table 1**. Biochemical parameters (**Table 2**) revealed an elevated level of carbohydrate reactive protein (CRP) and the figure of ASLO (antistreptolysin O) is increased sharply. Although, immune markers rised significantly especially, Anti-cyclic antibodies citrulline-containing (ACCP) on the **Table 3**. According to the last tables (**No.4 and No.5**), a serological study of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgM and G was determined. By this way, the anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG was positive. By the ultrasound of the knee joints revealed synovitis of both joints.

Table 1. Hematological Parameters of the JRA after Covid Patient During Diagnostic Work-Up

Parameter	Reference Range	Unit	Result
Hemoglobin (HB)	120-140	g/L	117
Red blood cells (RDC)	3.9-4.7	1012/L	4.87
Platelet count	180-320	109/L	373.0
Total leukocyte count	4.0-9.0	109/L	11.08
Stab Neutrophils	1-6	%	6.23
Segmented Neutrophils	47-72	%	43.9
Eosinophils	0,5-5	%	0.09
Monocytes	2-10	%	0.55
Lymphocytes	19-37	%	37.7
ESR	0-15	mm/hour	21.77

Table 2. Biochemical Parameters of the JRA after Covid Patient During Diagnosis

Carbohydrate reactive protein (CRP)	6	mg/L	24
Rhematoid factor	12	IU/L	6.3
ASLO (antistreptolysin O)	200	IU/L	1692.5

Table 3. Immune markers of the JRA after Covid Patient During Diagnosis

Name of analysis	Result	Norm
ANA Screen	42.35	negative: <40,0; positive: >40,0 AU/ml
Anti-cyclic antibodies citrulline-containing (ACCP)	21.75	0-17

Table 4. SARS-Cov-2 IGM

Name of analysis	Result	Norm
IgM anti SARS-COV-2	0.16	0-1.0 AU/ml

Table 5. SARS-Cov-2 IGG

Name of analysis	Result	Norm
IgG anti SARS-COV-2	72.0	0-1.0 AU/ml

Ultrasound of the knee joints

Right knee joint: the joint space is widened, the synovial membrane is uneven, the joint fluid is increased, heterogeneous with hyper and hypoechoic inclusions with a thickness of 15.2 mm.

Left knee joint: the joint space is widened, the synovial membrane is uneven, the joint fluid is increased, heterogeneous with hyper and hypoechoic inclusions with a thickness of 14.1 mm.

Conclusion: echogenic signs of inflammatory changes in the knee joints on both sides.

Conclusion. In this article, we reviewed the clinical picture and laboratory analysis of rheumatoid arthritis after Covid 19 with a favorable course and outcome in an early age boy.

The patient received anti-inflammatory and basic treatment several times in our clinic, now his general condition has improved, there is no fever, swelling in both knee joints has disappeared, movements have become freer, and in general the patient has entered a period of remission.

Currently available data suggest that IVRD, including RA, and PCD have a similar pathogenesis, determined by autoimmune reactions, the development of fibrosis, hypercoagulation and inflammation.

Our purpose in presenting this case report was, last year the indicate of the JRA after Covid 19 is rising and such patients come to our clinic from different regions of Uzbekistan. Unfortunately, clinical and specific treatments for early childhood rheumatoid arthritis after COVID-19 have not yet been developed. In such cases, it is necessary to quickly examine patients with COVID-19 and, if a marker of this infection is detected, immediately begin pathogenetic treatment. Considering the insufficient understanding of the etiology and the unknown consequences of MIS associated with SARS-CoV-2, patients need long-term monitoring of their follow-up.

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